

doi:10.5281/zenodo.15333585

Information and Communication Technology Skills and Teacher Performance in Public Secondary Schools in Port Harcourt Urban, Rivers State

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ABSTRACT

The purpose of this study was to examine the relationship between information and communication technology skills and teacher performance in public secondary schools in Port Harcourt Urban, Rivers State. The study was guided by two research questions. The study adopted a cross-sectional descriptive survey design with a population of 75 teachers in 5 public secondary schools in Port Harcourt Urban, Rivers State. A sample size of 63 teachers was drawn using Krejcie & Morgan Table on sample size determination. 63 copies of questionnaires were administered to respondents out of which 60 copies representing 95% were retrieved and found to be valid for the analysis. All items on the questionnaire had a Cronbach Alpha threshold of 0.857 and above in the reliability test. Mean scores descriptive statistics were used to answer the research questions. The result of the data analysed revealed that there was no relationship between information communication technology skills and teacher performance in public secondary school in Port Harcourt Urban, Rivers State. Based on the findings it was recommended that since teacher performance was unlikely to be largely influence by information and communication technology skills, improvement of pedagogical skills should be encouraged.

Keywords: Information Technology, Communication, Internet Skills, Teacher Performance

INTRODUCTION

Teacher performance is a critical factor in determining the quality of education and student outcomes. Studies have consistently highlighted the need for improved teacher performance to enhance student academic achievement and overall educational quality (Adejumo & Olatunji, 2014). The Nigerian government has also emphasized the importance of teacher development in achieving the country's educational goals (Federal Ministry of Education, 2017). Effective teachers not only impart knowledge but also inspire and motivate students to achieve their full potential. However, research has shown that teacher performance in public senior secondary schools in Nigeria faces significant challenges. Problems such as inadequate teacher training, limited resources, poor classroom management, and low teacher motivation have been identified as major hindrances to effective teaching and learning (Oyediran, Omoare, Owoyemi, Adejobi & Rafiat, 2020).

In recent years, Information and Communication Technology (ICT) has emerged as a potential solution to address these challenges. ICT skills have been recognized as essential for teachers to enhance their pedagogical practices, improve student engagement, and increase productivity (UNESCO, 2018). By

leveraging ICT, teachers can access vast educational resources, collaborate with colleagues, and develop innovative lesson plans.

The use of ICT in teaching is a relevant and functional way of providing education to learners in order to assist them in imbibing the required capacity for the world to work (Kosoko-Oyedeko & Tella, 2010). Davies (2009) posited that teachers use ICT to prepare for lessons and to deliver lesson in class. For lesson preparation, the following are the common pattern of ICT use. Teachers search the internet: download relevant materials; design practice activities with word processing, prepare presentations with Microsoft PowerPoint. However, for classroom teaching, PowerPoint presentation is popular. Teachers use the internet to supplement teaching points. Word processing is also used especially for writing classes, while voice recording is sometimes used for recording students' presentation or for pronunciation practice. Inevitably, computers were never developed for improving the quality of the teaching learning process, however, researchers started using computers for teaching purposes. This gave birth to Computer Assisted Instruction (CAI), Computer Managed Instruction (CMI), computer Based Instruction (CBI). People started developing CAI for teaching different subjects at the primary school and at the higher education level (Sansanwal, 2009).

This research focuses on ascertaining the relationship between information and communication technology skills and teacher performance in public secondary schools in Port Harcourt Urban, Rivers State. The study identified information and communication technology skills as a possible predictor of outcomes of teacher performance. Information and communication technology skills was in this light measured using two dimensions – office software application skills and internet navigation and research skills (Davies (2009). Thus, it provides a base for explaining and predicting changes and manifestation of teacher performance such as lesson planning, delivery and classroom management (Sansanwal, 2009).

Conceptual Framework

Figure 1: Conceptual framework showing the independent and dependent variables

Source: Researcher's desk (2025)

Office software applications are programs designed to facilitate various tasks related to office work, documentation, communication, and data management (Kroenke, 2019). They are commonly used in businesses, educational institutions, and personal productivity. Office Software Applications include word processing, spreadsheets, presentations, email and communication, desktop publishing and database management. In the context of teacher performance, office software applications are essential for teachers to create and edit lesson plans and education materials, track student grades and assessments,

communication with colleagues, parents and students, present educational content and analyse data for instructional decision making (Koehler & Mishra, 2020; Wiggins & McTighe, 2018)

Internet navigation refers to the process of finding and accessing information on the internet (Davies 2009). The key skills in internet navigation include Searching, Browsing, Bookmarking, and Filtering. Searching: Using search engines such as Google to find relevant information. Browsing: Exploring websites, hyperlinks, and online resources. Bookmarking: Saving favourite websites for future reference. Filtering: Evaluating online content for relevance and credibility. While Internet research requires systematically searching, evaluating, and synthesizing online information to answer questions or solve problems. Key Skills in Internet research include defining terms, using advanced search features, evaluating website credibility, identifying relevant online resources (Davies 2009).

Research emphasizes the importance of teacher performance in determining student outcomes. Key factors influencing teacher performance include teacher motivation and job satisfaction, classroom management and discipline and teacher-student interaction and relationships (Adejumo & Olatunji, 2014). Teachers' effectiveness is directly tied to their access to ongoing professional development opportunities. There are now significant obstacles that must be surmounted in regard to the quality of instructors, teaching techniques, and teacher education and training. According to Adejumo & Olatunji (2014), educators are struggling to meet students' needs in the classroom because they lack the necessary information and communication technology (ICT) professional and instructional abilities. Time constraints, rigid curricula, and a lack of information and communication technology (ICT) and ancillary staff services were cited by Sung, Yang & Lee (2017) who also identified other ICT barriers that prevent the improvement of teachers' professional skills, such as a lack of ICT resources and sustainability of the infrastructure, a lack of teachers' ICT pedagogical skills and attitudes, a lack of finances for purchasing technology, a lack of ICT teacher training, and a lack of teachers' motivation. Another key hindrance to improving the teaching and learning process, according to Cetin (2016), was a lack of training, knowledge, and abilities among teachers and students to make effective use of ICT instructional technology in the classroom. According to the Organisation of Economic Cooperation and Development (OECD), ICT was not fully integrated into classrooms as of 2016. Most teachers do not have the skills and knowledge they need to use technology well in the classroom.

Lesson plan delivery refers to the implementation of a well-structured plan to achieve specific learning objectives (Killen, 2017). Effective delivery involves introduction and hook: Engaging students with a relevant and interesting introduction (Petty, 2019); direct Instruction: explicit teaching and demonstration of concepts (Marzano, 2018); guided practice: students apply new knowledge with guidance (Johnson & Johnson, 2020); independent practice: students demonstrate mastery through autonomous work (Wiggins & McTighe, 2018); closure and assessment: evaluating student learning and providing feedback. Effective lesson delivery strategies include Differentiation: Tailoring instruction to meet diverse needs (Tomlinson, 2020); Technology Integration: Utilizing technology to enhance learning (Koehler & Mishra, 2020); Formative Assessment: Ongoing evaluation to inform instruction (Black & William, 2017).

Classroom management involves creating a productive learning environment (Emmer & Stough, 2020). Key components include classroom organization: Establishing a well-structured physical environment (Marzano, 2018); Behaviour management: Setting clear expectations and consequences (Albert, 2020); Time management: Maximizing instructional time (Wiggins & McTighe, 2018); Communication: Fostering positive relationships with students (Petty, 2019); Student Engagement: Encouraging active participation and motivation (Fredricks et al., 2020).

Effective classroom management strategies include establishing Clear Expectations: Setting clear rules and consequences (Marzano, 2018); Creating a Positive Learning Environment: Fostering respect and responsibility (Kagan, 2020); Minimizing Disruptions: Strategies to maintain focus (Emmer & Stough, 2020).

Li and Ma (2010) carried out a study on a meta-analysis of the Effects of Computer Technology (CT) on School Students' Mathematics Learning. Results indicated statistically significant positive effects of CT on mathematics achievement.

Uba (2012) carried out a study on the role of ICT in improving teacher performances. Finding shows that teachers have lots of difficulties implanting ICT.

Statement of the Problem

Research has been conducted on ICT from different perspectives, for instance Kochenbuger (2003) examined the use of computer in modern education system in developed world. Yusuf (2005) worked on the ICT and teacher education in Nigeria. Yusuf (2005) studied the need for the integration of ICT in Nigeria tertiary education.

The question is, are our teachers in Nigeria exposed enough to the varied technological facilities, virtual library, e-teaching and e-learning, that is to say the ICT demands of the age for qualitative education? That is then the background for which this study is based. Consequently, studies have confirmed that most of our teachers lacked basic computer resources, equipment or skills. This severally impacts on their ability to get most out of their learning experiences and their preparedness to accomplish their duty well in this modern world. Many of these teachers cannot incorporate ICT skills in their teaching, research and service to the schools where they teach. This technology deficit, therefore, translate into a major handicap in teaching and learning in our schools. Yusuf (2005) listed ICT facilities which should be mastered by teachers to include the radio, television, videos, computers, sensors interface boxes, e-mail satellite connection, internal software materials. All these must be employed by teachers for effective teaching and learning. These help to improve their performance.

However, there has been a dearth of research on the relationship between ICT skills and teacher performance in the context of public secondary schools in Port Harcourt Urban, Rivers State. This study aims to address this knowledge gap by investigating the relationship between ICT skills and teacher performance in public secondary schools in Port Harcourt Urban, Rivers State.

Purpose of the Study

The purpose of this study is to ascertain the relationship between information and communication technology skills and teacher performance in public senior secondary schools in Port Harcourt Urban, Rivers State.

The specific objectives of the study are to:

1. Ascertain the relationship between Office software application skills and teacher performance in public secondary schools in Port Harcourt Urban, Rivers State.
2. Ascertain the relationship between Internet navigation and research and teacher performance in public secondary schools in Port Harcourt Urban, Rivers State.

Research Questions

To find out how Information and Communication Technology skills affect teacher performance in public secondary schools in Port Harcourt Urban, Rivers State, the researcher sought answers to the following research questions:

1. What is the relationship between office software application skills and teacher performance in public secondary schools in Port Harcourt Urban, Rivers State?
2. What is the relationship between internet navigation and research skills and teacher performance in public secondary schools in Port Harcourt Urban?

METHODOLOGY

The study adopted a cross-sectional survey design method with a population of 75 teachers from 5 public secondary schools in Port Harcourt Urban, based on the data from Rivers State Post Primary Schools Management Board, Ministry of Education in Rivers State. In advancing the sample size for this research, the Krejcie and Morgan 1970 sample size determination table was adopted. A sample size of 63 teachers was determined and adopted for this research. The probability sampling method was adopted using the simple random sampling technique. The instruments for data collection were researcher-designed questionnaires titled “**Information and Communication Technology Skills and Teachers Performance in Public Secondary Schools in Port Harcourt Urban, Rivers State**”. The instrument comprises two sections: Section A and Section B. Section A was designed to collect the biodata of respondents while Section B comprises items aimed at providing relevant information in respect to the

research questions. Questionnaire items were designed on a five-point Likert scale of strongly Agree (SA)=1, Agree (A)=2, Neutral (N)=3, Disagree (D)=4 and Strongly Disagree (SD)=5. The instrument was validated by two experts. One in the field of Business Policy and the other in the field of Measurement and Evaluation at the Rivers State University. The internal consistencies of the instruments were determined using the Cronbach Alpha method which yielded a reliability index of 0.857, which showed that the instruments were reliable. Out of the 63 copies of the questionnaire administered, 60 were retrieved and used for the analysis. Mean scores were used to answer the researcher questions posed from the data generated in the study. Values were assigned to the opinion of the respondents as follows: Strongly agree = 1, Agree = 2, Neutral = 3, Disagree = 4, Strongly Disagree = 5, any mean score of 3.00 and above was rejected while any mean below 3.00 was accepted. All the statistical analyses will be performed using the Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS) version 26.0.

RESULTS

Research Question 1: *What is the relationship between office software application skills and teacher performance in public secondary schools in Port Harcourt Urban, Rivers State?*

Table 1: Descriptive Statistics on office software application skills and teacher performance

S/No	Item	Mean	Remark
1	I am proficient in using educational software to support my teaching	4.25	Disagree
2	I regularly use online resources to supplement my lesson plans	4.30	Disagree
3	I am confident in my ability to trouble shoot basic technical issues in the classroom	4.45	Disagree
4	I have received adequate training on the use of ICTs in teaching	4.45	Disagree
5	I use digital tools to assess student learning	4.35	Disagree
6	I am comfortable using ICTs to communicate with students and parents	4.30	Disagree
7	I regularly update my ICT skills to keep pace with new technologies	4.40	Disagree
8	I use ICTs to enhance student engagement and motivation	4.55	Disagree
9	I am able to effectively integrate ICTs into my lesson plans	4.50	Disagree
10	I use ICTs to support differentiated instruction	4.70	Disagree

Source: Research Data 2025

The data in table 1 illustrates the response rates and mean scores of office software application skills measured on a 5-item instrument and scaled on a 5-point Likert Scale. From the data, the first question shows a mean score of 4.25 which is on the disagree range of the scale. The 2nd, 3rd, 4th, 5th, 6th, 7th, 8th, 9th and 10th question item with 4.30, 4.45, 4.45, 4.35, 4.30, 4.40, 4.55, 4.50 and 4.70 respectively also imply that the respondents are more inclined to the disagreed range of the scale used in measurement. In all, the response distribution shows largely that information communication technology skills is an observed phenomenon among the sample.

Research Question 2: *What is the relationship between internet navigation and research skills and teacher performance in public secondary schools in Port Harcourt Urban, Rivers State?*

Table 2 Descriptive Statistics on internet navigation and research skills and teacher performance

S/No	Item	Mean	Remark
1	I use ICTs to support differentiated instruction	4.70	Disagree
2	My school provides adequate ICT infrastructure to support teaching and learning	4.50	Disagree
3	I have access to regular professional development opportunities to improve my ICT skills	4.65	Disagree
4	I use ICTs to enhance my teaching practice	4.55	Disagree
5	I am able to effectively use ICTs to support student learning outcomes	4.55	Disagree
6	My school encourages the use of ICTs in teaching and learning	4.45	Disagree
7	I use ICTs to support collaborative learning among students	4.45	Disagree
8	I am confident in my ability to use ICTs to support student assessment	4.35	Disagree
9	I regularly reflect on my use of ICTs in teaching and learning	4.20	Disagree
10	I use ICTs to support personalized learning for students	4.15	Disagree

Source: Study Data 2025

The data in table 2 illustrates the response rates and mean scores of internet navigation and research skills measured on a 5-item instrument and scaled on a 5-point Likert scale. From the data, the first question item shows a mean score of 4.70 which is on the disagree range of the scale. The 2nd, 3rd, 4th, 5th, 6th, 7th, 8th, 9th and 10th question items with 4.50, 4.65, 4.55, 4.55, 4.45, 4.45, 4.35, 4.20 and 4.15 respectively also imply that the respondents are more inclined to the disagreed range of the scale used in measurement. In all, the response distribution shows largely that internet navigation and research skills is an observed phenomenon among the sample.

DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

Table 1 reveals the relationship between office software application skills and teacher performance. Based on the mean score responses teachers in observed sample disagreed that: they are proficient in using education software to support teaching, they regularly use online resources to supplement their lesson plans, they disagreed that they are confident in their ability to trouble shoot basic technical issues in the classroom, they have received adequate training on the use of ICTs in teaching, they disagree that they use digital tools to assess student learning, they disagreed that they are comfortable using ICTs to communicate with students and parents, they disagree that they regularly update their ICT skills to keep pace with new technologies, they use ICT skills to enhance student engagement and motivation, they disagree that they are able to effectively integrate ICT skills into their lesson plans and use ICT skills to support differentiated instruction. These findings are consistent with Uba (2012) who posited that teachers have lots of difficulties implanting information and communications technology to improve their performance.

Table 2 reveals the relationship between internet navigation and research skills and teacher performance. Based on the mean score responses, teachers in observed sample disagreed that: use of ICT skills support differentiated instructions, their school provides adequate ICT infrastructure to support teaching and learning, that they have access to regular professional development opportunities to improve their ICT skills, that they use ICT skills to enhance their teaching practice, they are able to effectively use ICTs to support student learning outcomes, their school encourages the use of ICT teaching and learning, they use ICT skills to support collaborative learning among students, they are confident in their ability to use ICT skills to support student assessment, they regularly reflect on their use of ICTs in teaching and learning, they use ICT skills to support personalized learning for students. These findings are consistent

with Uba (2012) who posited that teachers have lots of difficulties implanting information and communications technology to improve their performance.

CONCLUSION

The purpose of this research was to ascertain the relationship between information and communication technology skills and teacher performance in public secondary schools in Port Harcourt Urban, Rivers State. From the data generated and analysed, it was observed that there was no relationship between information and communication technology skills and teacher performance in public secondary schools in Port Harcourt Urban, Rivers State.

RECOMMENDATION

Based on the discussions and conclusions reached from the study, since teacher performance is unlikely to be influenced by information and communication technology skills:

1. School administrators should encourage the improvement of pedagogical skills such as knowledge of various teaching methods like project-based learning, problem-based learning and differentiated instruction, effective communication skills, skills in using various questioning strategies to promote critical thinking, problem solving and student engagement and the ability to design and implement assessments that measure student learning and understanding should be encouraged.
2. The investigation of the relationship between office and information technology skills and teacher performance should be carried out as an empirical study addressing the concerns of teachers in public secondary schools in Port Harcourt Urban, Rivers State.

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